

Effects of high temperature on concentrations of soluble sugars and quercitol of Cork oak (*Quercus suber*) seedlings

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1- Abstract

The cork oak forms real cork woods which exploit an undeniable part the socio-economic plan in the Mediterranean basin. All times the multiple aggressions (overgrazing, repeated fires...), as well as the drought caused by the climate change (high temperatures) involving deteriorations and return the ecosystem to cork oak very sensitive to natural regeneration. To develop the problems and the causes affecting the reconstitution of the suberculture, the recourse to assisted regeneration and the various forestry treatments are a great need for the maintenance of its habitat. Regeneration by natural sowings remains insufficient whereas the forestations are generally lacking following none the control of the techniques of breeding of the seedlings in seedbed, and with the transplant shock due to the abrupt change in thermal conditions when moved from standard seedbed conditions to those of plantation sites often challenged with cold or heat stress. With an aim of evaluating the physiological behavior of cork oak with respect to the high temperatures, an experiment was led in conditions controlled in a culture room. Sowings of cork oak are cultivated in controlled conditions at 25°C and a 16-hr photoperiod. We have measured the content soluble sugar (sucrose, glucose, and fructose) and the content quercitol in the various organs of these sowings. Four thermal stresses (38, 40, 42 and 44°C) were applied; the results show that there is a significant reduction in the content soluble sugar. However, this species accumulates quercitol in these various organs to face the thermal stress (high temperatures).

Keywords: cork oak, high temperatures, soluble sugar, quercitol

2- Introduction

The cork oak (*Quercus suber* L.) is an endemic tree species from the Western Mediterranean basin and the coast of Morocco Atlantic (Seigue, 1985). In Algeria, this natural essence is one of the most notable among the forest formations but also one of the most valuable given the undeniable role of the cork oak forests on the environmental (erosion, fire resistance, carbon sequestration and the fight against the greenhouse effect) and socio-economic (quality of its wood and bark).

Indeed, Algeria provides 5% of world production of cork. This formation, despite its value, had known a continued decline and alarming translated by a regression in its surface of 440 000 to 229 000 hectares currently considered as productive (10% of the world cover) (Harfouche and al., 2003). This regression is the result of a bad management combined with the climate changes (Najeh, 2010) affecting the production of cork and those limiting natural regeneration.

The Algerian climate of Mediterranean type is characterized by an irregularity which appears by the disturbance of the modes of precipitations and the increase in the temperature. The projections of precipitations and the temperatures at the horizons 2020 and 2050 for the Mediterranean envisage a more important low of precipitations and an increase in average temperatures (Gracia, 2006 in Rego, 2006), just like a modification of their distribution (dry and hot summer, worsening the conditions of drought, and increasing the frequency of the extreme climatic events). The ecophysiological function of the cork oak is strongly affected by changing climatic upheavals as attests the works of Ghouil and al. (2003), Haldimann and Feller (2004) which treats the effect of temperature on the photosynthetic mechanisms of the cork oak. Other parameters also were the subject of several researches such as the increase of atmospheric CO₂ (Damesin and al., 1996), the drought stress (Flexas and al., 2002) and the increase of light (Aranda and al., 2007).

To give a first insight into the mechanism involved behind the response of cork oak seedlings to repetitive short-term exposure to high temperatures, we were focused on the impact of this abiotic constraint on the evolution of the principal biochemical markers to high temperatures such as soluble sugars (glucose, fructose, sucrose) and quercitol in the different organs of the plant. This is for aim of understanding the capacities of adaptation and the tolerance of oak cork at thermal variability (high temperatures).

3- Materiel and methods

Our study was carried out on cork oak seedlings (*Quercus suber* L.) from acorns collected on adult subjects of the region of the province of Skikda (Filfila, at the place called Col Besbes, Eastern- Algeria), in a sub-humid ambient weather with soft winter (m=10.55°C, M=24.25°C and P is 830 mm). The site of collection is situated closely at the intersection of parallel 36°37' of North latitude and of meridian 7°30' of East longitude at 500 m high. They were grown in plastic pots of a 50 cm of size and 60 cm deep, filled with peat (organic material 2%, dry material 3%, water retention 30%, pH=6.7 and resistivity 1200 ohm.cm).

The cork oak has an endogenous rhythmic growth that is expressed by the development of successive identically structural unities, called waves or flushes (Fig. 1). After the end of the second growth wave, the seedlings were successively subject to three treatments (3 x 3h) at the following temperatures: 38°C, 40°C, 42°C, 44°C, and 25°C (control).

Figure 1: Cork oak seedling with two waves (Alatou and al., 2007 in Rached-Kanouni and al., 2012).

3.1- Extraction of soluble sugars and quercitol

Soluble sugars and quercitol contained in the different organs are extracted by incubation of 20 mg of powder in 1 ml of ethanol at 80% for 30 minutes followed by a 14 000g centrifugation for 10 minutes. Three successive extractions are done in varying the ethanol solution used. During the 1st extraction, we use an ethanol solution at 80% containing mannitol at 0.125g/l which serves as a standard in dosages with HPLC. For the 2nd extraction, we again use ethanol at 80% but with no mannitol. Next, for the 3rd extraction, ethanol is at 50% in order to extract the hardly soluble metabolites in alcohol. Columns are prepared by the mains of pipettes ends cut at one end then filled as follows: (polyester fabric rug + 100µl Dowex 50 + 150 µl AGX + 400µl of the active charcoal + 100 PVPP). Active charcoal is only used in the event of alcohol extracts obtained from the powders of samples. It is used to eliminate the molecules not retained by PVPP and to clarify the extracts as well. PVPP serves to eliminate the big molecules and polyphenols. In priority, each column is moisturised again with 100 µl of ethanol at 80%. Likewise, a slight pressure is applied to enhance the passage of the alcohol extract. The purpose is to trap all the charged molecules. They then let only carbohydrates pass. The alcoholic extracts coming from all the three supernatant are filtered as they are collected. We rinse twice with 1 ml of ethanol at 80% before putting to dry the solutions therefore obtained with "Speed-vac" over one night. The soluble sugars and the quercitol are quantified with the HPLC.

3.2- Statistical Analysis

Results gotten of the studied parameters soluble sugars (sucrose, fructose and glucose) and quercitol have been interpreted statistically by the ANOVA to a factor by means of the

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analysis of the variance, while using the software Excel Stat (2009). This method serves to compare the different means with each other, for treatments and to look where averages are considered equal. If oppositely, there is a meaningful difference (theoretical Fischer value lower than the value of Fischer observed). The Newman-Keuls test at threshold 5% is carried on to complete the interpretation and identification of the homogeneous average groups.

4- Results and discussion

Owing to its deleterious effects on plant growth and development, high temperature stress causes considerable annual losses in plant productivity. Furthermore, global warming will likely aggravate its impact on agriculture and forestry in forthcoming years (Walther and al., 2002). In spite of substantial effort, breeding crops for higher thermotolerance has been much less successful than breeding for other agronomically relevant traits (Khush, 2001). Like other organisms, plants have evolved different mechanisms to withstand heat stress. These include a wide variety of long-term evolutionary adaptations affecting their morphology and ecophysiology, as well as shorter term acclimation mechanisms such as transpirational cooling, changes in leaf orientation, or alterations in membrane lipid composition (Larkindale and al., 2005a). Besides their inherent ability to withstand supraoptimal temperatures for short periods of time (basal thermotolerance), plants are able to become rapidly tolerant to otherwise lethal high temperatures (acquired thermotolerance). This response is triggered by prior exposure to a conditioning pretreatment, which can be a short, sublethal high temperature, a gradual temperature increase, or other moderate stress treatment (Boston and al., 1996).

The effect of high temperatures on cork oak seedlings appears primarily on the accumulation of certain solutes. The results obtained in this research show that this species accumulates to a significant degree of quercitol in these different organs (Fig. 2). Except for the temperature 44°C, where the leaves of the first growth flush of cork oak seedling transferred to a range of temperature between 38°C and 44°C during 3h accumulate more quercitol compared to the control (48%); the content quercitol for the other treatments remains similar to that of the control. It increases in a significant way in the leaves of the 2nd growth flush where it is 3 times more important at 44°C. As regards stems, increase content is obtained at 44°C (158%); whereas at 38°C and 40°C, the content remains identical to the control. the quercitol content of the roots is slightly higher than the control by reaching its maximum at 44°C (40%). The accumulation of the quercitol content in the different organs of cork oak seedlings increases proportionally with duration and the intensity of the thermal stress (high temperatures). Indeed, for durations of stress 6 and 9h, we have recorded rates of increase very high in all the organs but in a remarkable way in the leaves of the 2nd flush of growth and the roots of stressed sowings at 44°C during the period of 9h. These rates are respectively 540% and 515%.

Figure 2: Quercitol content in the different organs of cork oak seedlings. Bars represent means values (n=4). a: S1 (3h); b: S2 (6h) and c: (9h)

The quercitol concentrations were positively correlated with the intensity of high temperature. The correlation of changing environmental conditions with the concentration of sugars in the tissues is a common feature of various organs of deciduous woody species. In *Q. robur*, quercitol is the dominating cyclitol. It is found in leaves, twigs, bark and buds and contributes up to 65% to the neutral fraction and up to 3.3% to dry matter (Popp and al., 1997). In contrast, to other cyclitols such as ononitol, pinitol and quebrachitol, the cryoprotective effect of quercitol does not seem to be a specific, non-colligative one (Orthen and Popp, 2000); thus, its effect is likely to depend on its concentration. In our study, repeated thermal stress (high temperature) significantly increased the quercitol concentration of the different organs. Therefore, we have no clear evidence that an increase in the quercitol concentration contributes to the thermal stress induced increase in basal thermotolerance. We have recently shown that cyclitols accumulate to osmotically significant concentrations in leaves of a range of Australian tree species (Adams and al., 2005; Merchant and Adams 2005; Merchant and al., 2006), raising suggestions for their function as cellular osmotica.

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The results of figure 2 show that the lowest sucrose contents are found in the leaves of the sowings subjected to the stress duration of 9h, compared to the stems and the roots (more than 9 Mg. g-1 ms). In the leaves, a light accumulation of sucrose is observed at the sowings transferred at 38°C for the first two stresses (S1 and S2) and becomes more important in the stems and the roots. From 40°C, the reduction in sucrose increases according to the temperature and the duration of the stress. This is confirmed by the analysis of the variance with three fixed criteria ($p < 0.001$), where the sucrose content is always important at 38°C compared to the control and the other temperatures. Thus, the comparison of the sucrose contents in the different organs of seedlings according to the duration and intensity of the thermal stress applied watch that there is a clear sucrose increase in the roots compared to the stems and the leaves.

Figure 3: Sucrose content in the different organs of cork oak seedlings

The results of glucose and fructose content on the different organs of cork oak seedlings stressed are illustrated in figures 3 and 4. Their content increases slightly in the leaves of the 1st growth flush stressed at 38°C (S1: 3h) without being significant; whereas it decreases for the remaining treatments and the low rate low is obtained at 44°C, either 61% for the fructose and 114.71% for glucose in the transferred leaves three successive stresses (9h). In the leaves of the 2nd growth flush, their contents decrease significantly compared to the control and the lowest rate is recorded at 44°C (245% for fructose 286.5% for glucose). In the stems, an increase in glucose and fructose at 38°C and 40°C are obtained and of the reductions for the remaining treatments however were observed. In the roots, a very important reduction in glucose is observed starting from 38°C and reaches its maximum of 904% at 44°C for the duration 9h (3S). Contrary to glucose and except for the temperature 44°C or the roots contents of fructose similar present to the control; the roots stressed during the period of 3h and 6h accumulate more fructose with a high level at 38°C (103% for the stressed roots 3h and 52% per the duration of 6h).

The comparison of the averages on cork oak seedlings stressed by Anova with 5% show that the high temperatures induce a reduction in the accumulation of glucose and fructose compared to the control. Thus the leaves of the 1st flush of growth accumulate more of glucose and the fructose compared to the leaves of the 2nd growth flush, with the stems and the roots. The accumulation of glucose and the fructose is higher on the 1st stress compared to the other stresses.

Figure 4: Glucose content in the different organs of cork oak seedlings

Figure 5: Fructose content in the different organs of cork oak seedlings

The total sugar concentrations were negatively correlated with the thermal stress. However, sugars can function as cryoprotectants, which can non-specifically dilute the concentrations of compounds that are potentially toxic to proteins and membranes below the critical threshold of inactivation (Xin and Browse, 2000 in Marouani and al., 2001). Our tentative conclusion is that we have identified a cyclitol (quercitol) responsible for significant species and thermal stress condition-dependent variation in osmotic potential in cork oak seedlings.

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